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ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF SOIL FLUORINE CONTAMINATION ON MAIZE GROWTH AND VERIFICATION OF THE POSSIBILITY OF REDUCING PLANT F TOXICITY THROUGH THE ADDITION OF CALCIUM HYDROGEN PHOSPHATE (DCP) TO THE SOIL

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Soil contamination by fluorine (F) is known to inhibit plant growth. However, knowledge of the impact of soil F contamination on crop production remains limited. We assessed the impact of soil F contamination on maize (*Zea mays*) growth, whilst also verified the possibility of reducing plant F toxicity through the addition of calcium hydrogen phosphate (DCP), a recently focused F immobiliser, to the soil. In experiment number 1, soils were prepared by adding 10, 30, and 50 moles of F per 1 m³ of soil, respectively (F-10, F-30, F-50). These soils were filled into Wagner pots, and maize was cultivated. In experiment number 2, soil containing 50 mol of F per 1 m³ of soil was prepared. DCP was added to this F-contaminated soil at concentrations of 250 mol, 500 mol, and 1,000 mol per 1 m³ of soil (DCP-250, DCP-500, DCP-1,000). These soils were placed in Wagner pots, and maize was cultivated. For experiment number 1, the F-30 and F-50 showed clear growth inhibition 14 days after initiation (DAI). At the end of the cultivation (55 DAI), the dry matter yield of the F-30 and F-50 decreased by 70% and 84%, respectively, compared to the control without F addition. Thus, when the concentration of F added to the soil exceeded 30 mol/m³, maize growth was severely inhibited. For experiment number 2, treatment not mixed with DCP (negative control), growth was significantly inhibited due to F toxicity. In contrast, DCP-250, DCP-500, and DCP-1,000 all showed growth equivalent to the positive control (F-uncontaminated soil). At the end of cultivation (21 DAI), dry matter production in the DCP-250, DCP-500, and DCP-1,000 showed no statistically significant difference compared to the positive control. These results demonstrate that adding DCP to the soil can reduce the growth inhibition of plants in fluoride-contaminated soils.

Keywords: Calcium hydrogen phosphate (DCP), Fluorine toxicity to maize, Soil fluorine contamination, Plant growth test